

Correlation analysis of reactivity in the oxidation of substituted benzylamines by pyridinium hydrobromide perbromide

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The oxidation of benzylamine and twenty-seven *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-substituted benzylamines by pyridinium hydrobromide perbromide (PHPB), in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO), leads to the formation of the corresponding aldimines. The reactions are of first order with respect to both PHPB and the amine. The oxidation of deuterated benzylamine exhibited a substantial kinetic isotope effect ($k_H/k_D = 3.20$ at 303 K). An addition of pyridinium bromide does not affect the rate. PHPB itself has been postulated as the reactive oxidizing species. The rates of the oxidation of *para*- and *meta*-substituted benzylamines were correlated with Taft's and Swain's field and resonance substituent constants. The oxidation of *para*-substituted benzylamines showed an excellent correlation with Taft's σ_1 and $\sigma_R^{B\Delta}$ values; the *meta*-compounds correlated best with σ_1 and σ_R^0 values. Rates of the *ortho*-substituted compounds showed a significant correlation with Charton's triparametric equation. Suitable mechanism has been proposed.

Pyridinium hydrobromide perbromide (PHPB) is one of the quaternary ammonium polyhalides, which have been used as an effective halogenating and oxidizing agent in synthetic organic chemistry¹⁻³. The polyhalides are more suitable than molecular halogens because of their solid nature, ease of handling, stability, selectivity and excellent product yield. We have been interested in the kinetic and mechanistic aspects of oxidation by polyhalide compounds and many reports have been emanated from our laboratory⁴⁻⁹. A perusal of literature showed that the oxidation of monosubstituted benzylamines by PHPB has not been studied so far. The oxidation of benzylamine presents interesting possibilities. It is known to yield a large number of products including those resulting from the condensation of the intermediate products of the oxidation of the parent amine¹⁰. In addition benzamide, benzaldehyde and benzoic acid are also formed¹⁰. In continuation of our earlier work on polyhalide ions, we report here the kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of benzylamine and twenty-seven monosubstituted benzylamines by PHPB in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO). The major emphasis of this investigation is to correlate the structure and reactivity in this oxidation.

Results and discussion

The rates and other experimental data were obtained for all the amines. Since the results are similar, only representative data are reproduced here.

The oxidation of the benzylamines by PHPB results in the formation of the corresponding aldimine. Analyses of products and stoichiometric determinations indicate the following overall reaction.

Rate laws : The reactions were found to be first order with respect to PHPB. The individual kinetic runs were of strictly first order to PHPB. Further, the pseudo-first order rate constants, k_{obs} , does not depend on the initial concentration of PHPB. The reaction rate increases linearly with an increase in the concentration of amines (Table 1). Thus, the order of the reaction with respect to amine is also one.

Induced polymerization of acrylonitrile : The oxidation of benzylamine, in an atmosphere of nitrogen, failed to induce polymerization of acrylonitrile. Further, the addition of acrylonitrile had no effect on the reaction rate (Table 1).

Effect of substituent : The rates of the oxidation of benzylamine and twenty-seven monosubstituted benzylamines were determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters were calculated (Table 2).

Kinetic isotope effect : To ascertain the importance of the cleavage of the α -C-H bond in the rate-determining step, the oxidation of [1, 1-²H₂] benzylamine (PhCD₂NH₂) was studied. The results (Table 2) showed the presence of a substantial kinetic isotope effect ($k_H/k_D = 3.20$ at 303 K).

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of benzylamine by PHPB at 293 K

$10^3[\text{PHPB}]$ mol dm^{-3}	[Amine] mol dm^{-3}	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ s^{-1}
1.0	0.10	2.19
1.0	0.20	4.09
1.0	0.30	7.01
1.0	0.50	11.4
1.0	1.00	20.8
1.0	1.50	32.4
1.0	2.00	41.4
1.0	1.00	20.5 ^a
1.0	1.00	21.1 ^b
2.0	0.50	12.0
4.0	0.50	11.0
6.0	0.50	11.8
8.0	0.50	10.8

^a and ^b contained 0.005 and 0.01 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile respectively.

Effect of pyridinium bromide : The rates of oxidation were not affected by an addition of pyridinium bromide (Table 3).

A linear correlation ($r^2 = 0.9825$; slope = 0.7350 ± 0.0273) between $\log k_2$ at 293 K and at 323 K for benzylamine and twenty-seven monosubstituted benzylamines indicated that all the amines are oxidised by the same mechanism¹¹. A linear isokinetic relationship is a necessary condition for the validity of the linear free energy relationships. The value of the isokinetic temperature is 453 ± 25 K. At the isokinetic temperature, the reactions of all the compounds, so correlated, will proceed at almost equal rates. The fact that the isokinetic temperature, obtained in this reaction, is much higher than the experimental temperature range suggests that the difference in the reactivity of the amines decreases with an increase in temperature.

Table 2. Rate constants for the oxidation of substituted benzylamines by PHPB and the activation parameters

Subst.	$10^4 k_2/\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$				ΔH^* kJ mol^{-1}	ΔS^* $\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$	ΔG^* kJ mol^{-1}
	293 K	303 K	313 K	323 K			
H	9.85	20.8	42.8	85.0	54.0 ± 0.3	-119 ± 1	89.2 ± 0.2
<i>p</i> -NHCOMe	17.6	35.2	64.0	119	47.3 ± 0.5	-137 ± 2	87.9 ± 0.4
<i>p</i> -OMe	40.3	74.6	110	188	36.9 ± 1.4	-165 ± 4	85.9 ± 1.1
<i>P</i> -NO ₂	0.90	2.70	8.57	25.1	85.1 ± 1.1	-33 ± 4	94.7 ± 0.9
<i>p</i> -Me	17.0	32.9	61.2	113	47.1 ± 0.3	-138 ± 1	88.0 ± 0.2
<i>p</i> -F	12.5	26.4	50.7	103	52.4 ± 0.7	-122 ± 2	88.7 ± 0.6
<i>p</i> -Cl	6.00	13.8	30.8	68.0	61.1 ± 0.5	-99 ± 2	90.4 ± 0.4
<i>p</i> -Br	5.70	13.1	29.9	65.7	61.6 ± 0.5	-97 ± 2	90.5 ± 0.4
<i>p</i> -CF ₃	1.98	5.40	14.5	37.0	74.3 ± 0.6	-63 ± 2	92.9 ± 0.4
<i>p</i> -COOMe	2.58	6.49	17.2	43.4	71.7 ± 1.1	-70 ± 4	92.3 ± 0.9
<i>m</i> -NH ₂	20.0	39.7	76.0	148	49.8 ± 0.6	-127 ± 2	87.6 ± 0.5
<i>m</i> -OMe	11.9	24.0	49.8	99.0	53.2 ± 0.7	-120 ± 2	88.8 ± 0.6
<i>m</i> -Me	14.6	29.4	57.0	112	50.8 ± 0.6	-127 ± 2	88.3 ± 0.4
<i>m</i> -F	4.80	10.5	24.6	51.9	60.3 ± 0.9	-103 ± 3	90.9 ± 0.7
<i>m</i> -CF ₃	2.08	5.15	13.4	29.5	67.6 ± 0.8	-85 ± 3	92.9 ± 0.7
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	1.01	2.46	7.29	16.8	72.4 ± 1.8	-75 ± 6	94.6 ± 1.4
<i>m</i> -Cl	4.11	9.37	22.3	47.2	61.9 ± 0.7	-99 ± 2	91.3 ± 0.5
<i>m</i> -I	4.42	9.61	22.6	48.1	60.5 ± 1.0	-103 ± 3	91.2 ± 0.8
<i>m</i> -COOMe	2.99	6.61	16.5	35.9	63.3 ± 1.3	-97 ± 4	92.1 ± 1.0
<i>o</i> -Me	79.8	155	290	540	47.5 ± 0.4	-123 ± 1	84.1 ± 0.3
<i>o</i> -F	15.3	33.8	68.5	141	55.5 ± 0.5	-110 ± 2	88.1 ± 0.4
<i>o</i> -Cl	20.3	44.6	90.5	173	53.7 ± 0.4	-114 ± 1	87.4 ± 0.3
<i>o</i> -Br	28.2	60.3	124	238	53.5 ± 0.2	-112 ± 1	86.6 ± 0.2
<i>o</i> -NO ₂	1.77	4.48	10.0	21.7	63.0 ± 0.5	-102 ± 2	93.3 ± 0.4
<i>o</i> -NHCOMe	87.4	172	329	620	48.8 ± 0.4	-118 ± 1	87.0 ± 0.2

Table-2 (contd).

<i>o</i> -CF ₃	23.6	50.6	106	204	54.2 ± 0.3	-111 ± 1	87.0 ± 0.2
<i>o</i> -OMe	64.7	127	244	468	49.3 ± 0.5	-119 ± 2	84.7 ± 0.4
<i>o</i> -COOMe	9.87	21.5	44.8	91.4	55.8 ± 0.3	-113 ± 1	89.2 ± 0.2
[α,α- ² H ₂] benzylamine	3.31	6.51	13.2	27.5	54.3 ± 0.8	-127 ± 3	89.2 ± 0.2
<i>k_H/k_D</i>	3.15	3.20	3.24	3.09			

In solutions, PHPB may undergo the following reactions.

The probable oxidizing species in a solution of PHPB are, therefore, PHPB itself, tribromide ion and molecular bromine. However, a strict first order dependence on PHPB and the absence of any effect of pyridinium bromide are reminiscent to the results obtained in the oxidation of aromatic aldehydes by PHPB⁹. These observations rule out both bromine and tribromide ion as the reactive oxidizing species. Hence PHPB itself is the reactive oxidizing species in this reaction. Similar oxidizing species is suggested in the oxidation of aromatic aldehydes by PHPB⁹.

Correlation analyses of reactivity :

(i) *para*- and *meta*-substituted benzylamines : The rates of the *para*- and *meta*-compounds failed to exhibit a sig-

nificant correlation in terms of Hammett¹² or Brown's¹³ substituent constants (eqs. 4 and 5).

$$\log k_2 = -1.47 \pm 0.11 \sigma - 2.88 \quad (4)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9167; sd = 0.13; n = 19; \psi = 0.30; T = 293 \text{ K}$$

$$\log k_2 = -1.00 \pm 0.09 \sigma^+ - 3.05 \quad (5)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8770; sd = 0.16; n = 19; \psi = 0.36; T = 293 \text{ K}$$

Since the rates of oxidation of the monosubstituted benzylamines failed to show satisfactory correlation with any single substituent parameter equation, the rates of *para*- and *meta*-substituted benzylamines were subjected to analyses in terms of dual substituent parameter (DSP) equations of Taft¹⁴ and Swain *et al.*¹⁵. The rates of oxidation of the *para*- and *meta*-compounds were separately correlated with σ_I and four different σ_R values in Taft's equation¹⁴ and with the field and resonance substituent constants of Swain *et al.*¹⁵. The results are summarized in Table 4.

Both the *meta*- and *para*-series of substituted benzylamines meet the requirement of minimum number of substituents for analysis by DSP equations¹⁶. In this set of correlation analysis, the intercept was forced through origin.

Table 3. Effect of pyridinium bromide on the rate of oxidation

[PHPB] = 0.001 mol dm ⁻³ , [amine] = 2.0 mol dm ⁻³ , temp. = 303 K						
[PyHBr]/mol dm ⁻³	0.0	0.01	0.02	0.04	0.08	0.12
10 ⁴ <i>k</i> _{obs} /s ⁻¹	41.4	42.6	41.0	41.2	43.0	40.9

Table 4. Correlation of rate constants of the oxidation of *para*- and *meta*- substituted benzylamines with dual-substituent parameters

Subst.	ρ_I	ρ_R	R^2	<i>sd</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>n</i> ^a
(i) <i>para</i> -Substituted						
σ_I, σ_R^0	-1.20 ± 0.06	-1.95 ± 0.10	0.9849	0.065	0.071	10
σ_I, σ_R^{BA}	-1.24 ± 0.01	-1.57 ± 0.01	0.9995	0.011	0.012	10
σ_I, σ_R^-	-1.27 ± 0.15	-0.85 ± 0.12	0.9359	0.138	0.152	9 ^b
σ_I, σ_R^+	-1.27 ± 0.11	-0.92 ± 0.08	0.9520	0.117	0.130	10
Swain <i>et al.</i> ^c	-0.48 ± 0.03	-0.52 ± 0.03	0.9831	0.069	0.076	10
(ii) <i>meta</i> -Substituted						
σ_I, σ_R^0	-1.30 ± 0.01	-0.97 ± 0.01	0.9997	0.008	0.011	10
σ_I, σ_R^{BA}	-1.2 ± 0.04	-0.67 ± 0.48	0.9849	0.053	0.070	10
σ_I, σ_R^-	-1.11 ± 0.05	-0.71 ± 0.06	0.9779	0.064	0.084	10
σ_I, σ_R^+	-1.28 ± 0.08	-0.37 ± 0.05	0.9556	0.091	0.120	10
Swain <i>et al.</i>	-0.68 ± 0.03	-0.26 ± 0.02	0.9842	0.054	0.071	10

^aTemperature 293 K, *sd* = standard deviation, *f* = *sd*/root mean square of log *k/k*₀; σ_I and σ_R values are from Ref. 14. ^bData for NHCOME not considered; no σ_R^- value is available; ^cField and resonance substituent constants are from Ref. 15.

The rates of oxidation of the *para*-substituted benzylamines show an excellent correlation with Taft's σ_I and σ_R^{BA} values. We have used the standard deviation (*sd*), coefficient of multiple determination (R^2), and parameter *f* as the criteria of goodness of fit. *f* has been defined¹⁴ as $f = sd/RMS$, where RMS is the root mean square of the data (here $\log k/k_0$). Comparison showed that *f* is smaller for the σ_R^{BA} scale than for the other scales by factors of *ca.* 6 to 12. Thus, it is apparent that the rates of oxidation of *para*-substituted benzylamines by PHPB correlate best with σ_I and σ_R^{BA} .

The rates for the *meta*-substituted benzylamines show an excellent correlation with σ_I and σ_R^{BA} , though the discriminating factor for the precision of fit with the other σ_R scales or with Swain's equation is not very sharp. This agrees with the observation of Ehrenson, Brownlee and Taft¹⁷ that the correlation of *meta*-substituted compounds is generally best with the σ_R^0 scale and that *meta*-substituted compounds are less discriminating.

The reaction constants and statistical data at various temperatures are given in Table 5.

The value of λ^p (≈ 1.3) showed that the oxidation of *para*-substituted benzylamines is more susceptible to the resonance effect than to the field effect. In the reaction of the *meta*-substituted compounds, however, the value of λ^m is *ca.* 0.76, indicating the greater importance of the field effect. In both the cases, the magnitude of the reaction constants decreases with an increase in the temperature. This showed a decrease in selectivity with an increase in the temperature.

(ii) *ortho*-Substituted benzylamines : It has been stated that¹⁸ in the absence of proximity effects, the polar effects of the *ortho*-substituents ought to be parallel to those of *para*-substituents. However, in the present case it was found

that the rate constants of the *ortho*- and corresponding *para*-substituted compounds are not linearly related [eq. 6]. This indicated that polar effects alone are not sufficient to explain the observed effect of the *ortho*-substituents on the reaction.

$$\log k_{ortho} = 0.80 \pm 0.22 k_{para} - 3.35 \quad (6)$$

$$r^2 = 0.6179; sd = 0.34; n = 10; \psi = 0.65; T = 293 \text{ K}$$

The rate constants of the *ortho*-compounds were analysed in terms of σ_0 values of Tribble and Traynham¹⁹ also. The correlation was not satisfactory [eq. 7]. The unsatisfactory correlation and the fact that the value of k_2 for an *ortho*-substituted benzylamines is always greater than that of the corresponding *para*-compounds indicate that there is a significant steric effect of the *ortho*-substituents in this reaction.

$$\log k_2 = 0.80 \pm 0.25 \sigma_0 - 2.42 \quad (7)$$

$$r^2 = 0.3941; sd = 0.31; n = 9; \psi = 0.83; T = 293 \text{ K}$$

The data of *o*-NO₂ was not included in this correlation since the σ_0 value was not available.

The rates were, therefore, analysed by using Charton's method²⁰. The rates were correlated by using eqs. (8) and (9), where σ_I , σ_R and *V* are field, resonance and steric substituent constants; the values used were those compiled by Aslam *et al.*²¹. In this set of correlation analyses, the intercept was not forced through origin. The results of correlation analyses in terms of eq. (8) is given in eq. (10), where *n* is number of data points and ψ is the Exner's parameter²².

$$\log k_{ortho} = \rho_I \sigma_I + \rho_R \sigma_R + h \quad (8)$$

$$\log k_{ortho} = \rho_I \sigma_I + \rho_R \sigma_R + \phi V + h \quad (9)$$

$$\log k_2 = -1.23 \pm 0.56 \sigma_I - 1.23 \pm 0.49 \sigma_R - 2.47 \quad (10)$$

$$R_2 = 0.6080; sd = 0.36; n = 10; \psi = 0.70; T = 293 \text{ K}$$

Table 5. Temperature dependence of the reaction constants for the oxidation of *para*- and *meta*-substituted benzylamines by PHPB

Temp./K	ρ_I	ρ_R^b	λ^a	R^2	<i>sd</i>	<i>f</i>
(ii) <i>para</i> -Substituted						
293	-1.24 ± 0.01	-1.57 ± 0.01	1.27	0.9995	0.011	0.012
303	-1.05 ± 0.01	-1.38 ± 0.01	1.31	0.9997	0.008	0.009
313	-0.83 ± 0.03	-1.06 ± 0.01	1.28	0.9995	0.008	0.009
323	-0.62 ± 0.01	-0.85 ± 0.01	1.37	0.9989	0.009	0.010
(ii) <i>meta</i> -Substituted						
293	-1.30 ± 0.01	-0.97 ± 0.01	0.75	0.9997	0.008	0.011
303	-1.21 ± 0.01	-0.89 ± 0.01	0.74	0.9996	0.008	0.011
313	-1.00 ± 0.01	0.76 ± 0.01	0.76	0.9997	0.005	0.007
323	-0.91 ± 0.01	-0.71 ± 0.02	0.78	0.9996	0.006	0.008

^a $\lambda = \rho_R/\rho_I$, $f = sd/\text{root mean square of } \log k/k_0$, ^b ρ_R is ρ_R^{BA} and ρ_R^0 for *para*- and *meta*-substituted compounds respectively.

In multiple linear regression analyses using eq. (8), the coefficient of multiple determination is poor and *sd* is high [eq. 10]. The absence of a significant correlation with eq. (8) leads to the conclusion that the electric effects alone are not sufficient to account for the effect of the *ortho*-substituent effects in this reaction.

The correlation with eq. (9) was performed with rate data obtained at different temperatures and the results are summarized in Table 6. The reactions exhibited excellent correlation in terms of eq. (9).

Table 6. Temperature dependence of the reaction constants of the oxidation of *ortho*-substituted benzylamines by PHPB

Temp./K	ρ_I	ρ_R	ϕ	R^2	<i>sd</i>	P_R	P_S
293	-1.56 (±0.01)	-1.41 (±0.01)	1.29 (±0.01)	0.9998	0.008	47.5	30.3
303	-1.43 (±0.01)	-1.33 (±0.01)	1.23 (±0.01)	0.9997	0.009	48.2	30.8
313	-1.36 (±0.02)	-1.27 (±0.01)	1.19 (±0.01)	0.9997	0.011	48.3	31.2
308	-1.29 (±0.02)	-1.23 (±0.02)	1.14 (±0.02)	0.9995	0.012	48.8	31.1

^aNo. of data points = 10, σ_I , σ_R and *V* values are from Ref. 20.

The effects of the nitro and ester groups are consistent with their orthogonal configuration. The significance of the correlation was tested by means of an *F*-test²³. The confidence levels of the *F*-test are >99.9%. The confidence level for the significance of ρ_I , ρ_R and ϕ terms was evaluated by means of a Student's *t*-test²³. The confidence level of the *t*-test is >99.9%, indicating the operation of significant inductive, resonance and steric effects.

To test the significance of σ_I and σ_R when *V* is included, multiple linear regression analyses were carried out with σ_I and *V*, and with σ_R and *V*. The absence of significant correlations [eqs. 11 and 12] showed that both σ_I and σ_R are significant.

$$\log k_2 = -1.45 \pm 0.62 \sigma_I + 1.09 \pm 0.52 V - 2.61 \quad (11)$$

$$R^2 = 0.5380; sd = 0.40; n = 10; \psi = 0.76; T = 293 \text{ K}$$

$$\log k_2 = -1.32 \pm 0.51 \sigma_R + 0.99 \pm 0.49 V - 3.39 \quad (12)$$

$$R^2 = 0.5784; sd = 0.36; n = 10; \psi = 0.73; T = 293 \text{ K}$$

It is apparent from these results that the reaction belongs to case 1 of the classification given by Charton²⁰. There is no significant collinearity between σ_I and σ_R , σ_I and *V*, and σ_R and *V* ($r^2 = 0.0014, 0.0464$ and 0.0168 respectively) for the ten substituents. The contribution of the resonance effect²⁰ to the polar effect is given by eq. (13).

$$P_R = \frac{100 \times |\rho_R|}{|\rho_I| + |\rho_R|} \quad (13)$$

The contribution of the steric parameter²⁰ to the total effect of the substituent, P_S , was determined by using eq. (14).

$$P_S = \frac{100 \times |\phi|}{|\rho_I| + |\rho_R| + |\phi|} \quad (14)$$

The values of P_R and P_S are also recorded in Table 7. The magnitudes of P_R show that the field effect is more dominant than the resonance effect. The values of P_S show that there is considerable steric effect in this reaction.

It is of interest to compare the values of the reaction constants of the three series of compounds. The values of ρ_I of the *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-substituted compounds, at 293 K, are -1.56, -1.30 and -1.24 respectively i.e. the magnitude of the reaction constant decreases as the substituent moves away from the reaction centre. On the other hand the values of ρ_R are -1.41, -0.97 and -1.57 respectively. This showed that the magnitude of ρ_R follows the order : *para* > *ortho* > *meta*. Both the trends are in the expected direction. The less pronounced resonance effect from the *ortho*-position than from the *para*-position may be due to the twisting away of the methylamino group from the plane of the benzene ring.

Mechanism : A hydrogen abstraction mechanism leading to the formation of free radicals may be discounted in view of the failure to induce polymerization of acrylonitrile²⁴ and large value of reaction constants. In most hydrogen abstraction reactions, the reaction constants have small magnitude¹².

The negative polar reaction constant points to an electron-deficient carbon centre in the transition state of the rate-determining step. However, the low magnitudes of the polar reaction constants indicate a less pronounced charge separation in the transition state. The positive steric reaction constant indicates a steric acceleration of the reaction.

This may be explained on the basis of the high ground state energy of the sterically crowded amines. Since the crowding is relieved in the product aldimine as well as in the transition state leading to it, the transition state energy of the crowded and uncrowded amines do not differ much and steric acceleration, therefore, results.

The temperature invariance of the primary kinetic isotope effect (*cf.* Table 2) can be interpreted in terms of a mechanism in which two bonds are cleaved more or less synchronously. Therefore, a rate-determining step involving cleavage of both the C-H and N-H bonds can be envis-

aged. The low magnitude of the polar reaction constants also supports the occurrence of a synchronous mechanism. However, the correlation analyses of the substituent effect indicated the presence of an electron-deficient carbon centre in the transition state. It seems, therefore, that in the transition state the cleavage of the C–H bond, yielding an electron-deficient carbon centre, is somewhat ahead of the cleavage of the N–H bond. The transition state remains polar in this mechanism. A nonlinear transition state, implied in the synchronous mechanism, is supported by the relatively low magnitude of the kinetic isotope effect ($k_H/k_D \approx 3.2$) also. The oxidation of benzyl amine by benzyltrimethylammonium tribromide (BTMAB) also was reported⁸ to involve a synchronous cleavage of both C–H and N–H bonds via a non-linear transition state and the kinetic isotope effect was found to be about 3.3. The mechanism depicted in Scheme 1 accounts for all the observed results.

Scheme 1

It is of interest to compare the results of the oxidation of benzylamines by different oxidants. The rates of oxidation of *meta*- and *para*-substituted benzylamines by permanganate²⁵ ion correlate with σ^+ values, the reaction constant, ρ , being -0.28 . The small value of ρ suggested the possibility of a one-electron oxidation. In the oxidations by *N*-bromoacetamide (NBA)²⁶, *N*-chlorosuccinimide (NCS)²⁷ and hexamethylenetetramine-bromine (HABR)²⁸, the rates of the oxidation of monosubstituted benzylamines exhibited large negative polar reaction constants and a substantial kinetic isotope effects. A strong resonance interaction between the substituent and a developing positive charge, in the transition state, is also indicated. Hence, a one electron oxidation can be excluded. The mechanisms proposed for the oxidation of amines by NBA, NCS and HABR are essentially same, involving transfer of a hydride ion from the amine to the oxidant leading to the formation of a cationic species in the rate-determining step. The oxidation by BTMAB⁸ also exhibited negative polar reaction constants but the magnitudes are low. Further, the reactions showed substantial kinetic isotope effect but its magnitude is low and it is invariant with temperature. Therefore, the reaction

is proposed to involve a synchronous mechanism and a rate-determining step involving cleavage of both the C–H and N–H bonds are envisaged with the proposition that the cleavage of the C–H bond is ahead of the N–H bond. Similar results are observed in the present reaction and therefore, the mechanism suggested in the present reaction is essentially same to that of oxidation by BTMAB.

Experimental

PHPB was prepared by the reported method¹ and its purity was checked by an iodometric method. [α, α -²H₂]Benzylamine was prepared by the reduction of phenyl cyanide with lithium aluminium deuteride²⁹. Its isotopic purity, determined by the ¹H NMR spectra, was $93 \pm 2\%$. *m*-Amino- and *o*-nitrobenzylamines were prepared by the reported methods^{30,31}. The other amines were commercially available and were purified by distillation and recrystallization. DMSO was purified by the usual methods³².

Product analysis : The oxidation of benzylamines leads to the formation of the corresponding aldimines. The quantitative product analysis was carried out under kinetic conditions. In a typical experiment, benzylamine (1.07 g, 0.01 mol) and PHPB (0.32 g, 0.001 mol) were made up to 50 ml in DMSO and kept in the dark for *ca.* 12 h to ensure completion of the reaction. The amount of aldimine formed was then determined by the reported 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine method³³. In this method the aldimine is hydrolysed to the aldehyde and then isolated as 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (DNP), vacuum dried, weighed, recrystallized from ethanol and weighed again. The yields of DNP before and after recrystallization were 0.202 g (92%) and 0.175 g (76%) respectively. The DNP was found identical (m.p. and mixed m.p.) with the DNP of benzaldehyde. In similar experiments, with the other substituted benzylamines, the yields of DNP after recrystallization were in the range of 67–83%.

Stoichiometry : To determine the stoichiometry, PHPB (1.60 g, 0.005 mol) and benzylamine (0.107 g, 0.001 mol) were diluted to 50 ml in DMSO. The reaction mixture was kept in the dark for *ca.* 12 h to ensure completion of the reaction. The residual PHPB was determined spectrophotometrically at 358 nm. Several determinations, with differently substituted benzylamines, showed that the stoichiometry is 1: 1.

Kinetic measurements : The reactions were studied under pseudo-first order conditions by keeping an excess ($\times 15$ or greater) of the substrate over PHPB. The solvent was DMSO. The reactions were studied at constant temperature and were followed by monitoring the decrease in the concentration of PHPB at 358 nm for upto 80% reaction.

Pseudo-first order rate constants, k_{obs} were evaluated from linear plots ($r^2 > 0.990$) of $\log [\text{PHPB}]$ against time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants are reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$. Simple and multivariate regression analyses were carried out by the least-squares method.

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